

ROLE OF ISLAMIC BANKING & TAKAFUL FOR GROWTH OF EACH OTHER

by Dr. Abdul Qadir, Ataullah

Submission date: 07-Apr-2023 06:01AM (UTC+0500)

Submission ID: 2058008894

File name: 01._Role_Of_Islamic_Banking.docx (47.44K)

Word count: 2632

Character count: 13979

ROLE OF ISLAMIC BANKING & TAKAFUL FOR GROWTH OF EACH OTHER

Dr. Abdul Qadir

Assistant Professor, Department of Islamic Studies, Bahria University Karachi.

Ataullah

Ph.D. Researcher, Sheikh Zaid Islamic Center, University of Karachi.

Abstract

Current financial system of the world comprises of many basic elements. Banks and insurance companies are among those elements but the Muslims around the world have a long history of arguments on the validity of conventional banking and insurance and they felt need of an Islamic financial system to fulfill their financial requirements. It led the Muslim scholars to introducing alternates for both of them. The Islamic banking and Takaful were introduced as the alternates of conventional banking and insurance respectively. In conventional financial system banks and insurance companies help each other and this leads the system as a whole to a vital growth. As Muslims want to promote Islamic financial system, they will need to promote the cooperation between Islamic banking and Takaful. Along with other elements, Takaful companies and Islamic banks must help each other for the development and success of an Islamic financial system. This paper throws lights on the needs and importance of this cooperation between these two pillars of Islamic financial system and discusses the related issues in this regard.

Key words: *Insurance, Takaful, Islamic Insurance, Islamic Banking, Islamic Finance.*

DOI:

Introduction

Current financial system comprises of different pillars such as banking, insurance, capital and money market. The success and development of this system depends on the cooperation and interaction among these pillars. Banking and insurance were declared void by the majority of Muslim scholars and the Muslims of the world were in a need to their alternatives. Islamic banking emerged as an alternative to the conventional banking and the Takaful system was introduced as an alternative of conventional insurance system.

It is observed that interest in Islamic finance is growing globally so, the need for cooperation among the basic branches of the Islamic financial system must be growing too and it is also observed that the growth of Islamic banking as compare to conventional banking is higher, similarly on the other end the growth of Takaful and Re-Takaful is with significant ratio too high over the insurance and re-insurance. The global Takaful industry record a 12% year-on-year growth in contribution while conventional insurance premiums only grew by 4% in 2016 according to the IFSB's

Islamic Financial Services Industry Stability Report 2017¹ and SBP-Islamic Bulletin Report² June 2017.

It is a fact that banking and insurance industries play an important role in financial market for establishing a strong and smooth conventional financial system therefore strong relationship is required between conventional banking and insurance industry to maintain the conventional financial system, the same relationship will be required between Islamic banking and Takaful industries as the both are in nature alternatives for conventional banking and insurance so that the strong Islamic financial may developed for the benefit of both Muslims and non-Muslims. The Islamic financial system needs strong relationship among the Islamic financial institutions specially the Islamic banking and Takaful.

Literature Review:

Many studies have been done on the contribution and potential of Islamic banking and Takaful for the growth of economy. Trokic (2017) had shown the significance of the Takaful industry and the increasing Muslim population in America and Europe is considered a big opportunity for the development of the industry in these regions. Saleem (2008) has brought in his view, the real meaning of development if his study and the roles of Islamic banks in achieving that development.

Qorchi (2005) feels the potential of development in Islamic finance is hindered by the role of regulators, if the regulators take good steps for the Islamic finance it may gear up significantly.

PAN (2016) has worked on the relationship between insurance and banking sectors in China. His study shows that insurance and banking are interlinked industries and they can work for each other. The downward of banking effects the insurance industry and changes in the insurance industry may cause the banking sector change in the opposite direction.

Lorent (2010) discussed the link between insurance and banking sector with special regard to life insurance. He discussed the bancassurance strategy of banks and insurance industries. He thinks that this strategy worked better in the supply of life insurance.

Helmy (2012) showed the higher need of Islamic banks for risk cover in his study. He also discussed different risks that Islamic banks face and discussed the different risk management tools.

Research Methodology

This paper is written using a qualitative approach based on some interviews as primary

resources and on secondary resources through the method of document analysis.

Why Islamic finance?

Muslim jurists declared conventional banking and insurance non-Shariah compliant due to the elements of Riba (Interest) / Gharar (Uncertainty) and that led to think about alternatives of them. It was must for the alternatives to not contain non-Shariah complaint elements so, it resulted in emergence of the current Islamic banking (asset based not loan based) and Takaful industry (based on non-commutative contract).

What are the basic elements of Islamic finance?

But the need of an Islamic financial system could not be fulfilled without a complete solution to the financial requirements of the people. There for it was must to offer the willing individuals and corporate entities a full bunch of products that meet their necessities. Just like conventional financial system, Islamic financial system is also comprised of different components, the Islamic banking, the Takaful, the Islamic capital and money market etc. And the stronger the correlation of the components is, the higher the chances of success for the system are.

Correlation of Banking and Insurance

Banking and insurance have their distinct definitions and field of working, banks play their role in payment and settlement system, and they are involved in the transition of monetary policy, while insurers are not. But one can find some similarities in few of their functions. For instance, the main feature of banking is saving and investment, but we can find the same in policies of life insurance.

At the capital level we find many insurance companies are owned by bankers. At business level Bancassurance is increasing cross selling. At product level one may observe similarities in few life insurance products and banking products such as saving, and investment are known as functions of a bank and they are present in life insurance policies too. This creates a competition or substitution link between banks and insurance companies. (PAN 2016)

Banks are getting benefit by the mortgage coverage service of insurance which is encouraging bank borrowings for the common borrowers (Grace and Rebello 1993). So, the correlation of banking and insurance may be observed in various forms. One of the basic rules of insurance is 'law of large number', banks too create pools based on this law. (Lewis 1990)

It is also found by some researchers that property insurance activities can promote bank credit market by transferring the risks. (Zou 2006)

Banks give a big volume of business to the insurance companies and these companies invest their balance fund in TDRs.

The need of Islamic banking and Takaful and their market position

4

The Takaful is an important component of the Islamic financial system, and it is one of the fastest growing industries in the world. The number of the Takaful companies is growing day by day. It plays different roles in the financial activities. Long term funds are mobilized by the Takaful. Takaful companies are well established and organized institutions for long-term funds. The Takaful system also has its role in the overall development of the economy.

The statistics show that the demand of Islamic banking and Takaful is growing with the passage of time as mentioned earlier that there is a growth of 12% year-on-year for the industry.

Correlation of Islamic Banking and Takaful

Islamic banking and Takaful are interlinked industries. Islamic banks need risk coverage for their financial products and Takaful companies need Shariah compliant investment portfolios with low or moderate risk levels.

Banking has two major portions namely consumer and corporate. The main areas of services on the consumer side are auto and home financing.

Auto financing is either based on Ijarah or on Diminishing Musharakah. The home financing is normally based on the DM.

As normally Ijarah and DM transactions are used for long term financing so in Ijarah and DM the ownership of banks remains till the end of period and Islamic banks in nature as Ameen and Wakeel of the depositors are responsible to manage risk related to the ownership.

On the corporate side the product of Murabaha, Salam, Istisna and Musawama are practiced for short time financing. Although in normal Murabaha cases the ownership of Islamic banks does not last for long time but in Salam, Istisna and Musawama based transactions it lasts much longer as normally the ownership of Islamic banks remains on the goods of these transactions over the period of four to five months, depends on nature of client's business.

In the lights of the above facts, it is clear that Islamic banks face the higher level of risk in their products than the conventional banks and they need these risks to be covered. In our view it must be mandatory by the regulatory to cover these risks by Takaful

services and Islamic banks must not be allowed to cover these risks by conventional insurance. This might not be on the basis of entering an Aqd e Batil but for the sake of Islamic financial system it should be mandatory. We could not find any strict instruction or guideline by SBP in this particular issue. Only in Ijarah mode of finance in which sole ownership of Islamic banks remains for long term period SBP as a regulator mentioned preferable to seek Takaful coverage.

Now the practice whether Islamic banks should insure goods of Salam, Istisna and Muswama in short term financing and Ijarah and DM in long term financing under Takaful coverage from Takaful companies or insurance companies it depends on the policy and guidelines of Shariah board of Islamic banks.

The normal practice of the Islamic banking industry of Pakistan is observed that in auto finance as the vehicle comes in the name of Islamic banks they seek Takaful coverage due to their strong relationship with Takaful companies and in DM basis transactions probably the same practice is followed however in corporate financing the decision of insurance of goods depends on the nature of client who availing the facility from Islamic banks. Normally clients are initially associated with insurance companies and due to their decent rates and satisfied facilities they prefer insurance companies.

As the components of Islamic financial system Islamic banking and Takaful should cooperate with each other. Takaful works on the law of large number and Islamic banks can help the Takaful industry by maximizing the number of participants for the Takaful pools.

It can be done through bancatakaful activity in which banks offer the Takaful services to their clients within their premises. It is also possible by counseling of those clients who are not agreed to take Takaful coverage for their goods by clearing their doubts about Takaful and its services.

Normally Takaful operators do not have capacity of covering huge risks and this is one of the reasons for clients of the banks to prefer insurance over Takaful. Islamic banks can help the Takaful industry by establishing new Takaful companies which cooperate among them.

In 2012 Meezan Bank of Pakistan had shown its interest in establishing a full fledged Takaful company as its subsidiary but it could not happen yet for unknown reasons.³

Challenges faced by Takaful

Looking to the potential of the Takaful we feel its progress is very slow. There might be multiple reasons behind that. Following are some of them.

Underwriting Surplus Issue

In insurance industry when a client's claim experience is very good the insurance company shares underwriting surplus with him and this play a big role in strengthening of the insurer-insured relationship.

Takaful is introduced as a non-commutative contract and this is the main feature which is to be called the difference between conventional insurance and Takaful. This feature does not allow Takaful fund to share any profit as under writing surplus because this is against the nature of a non-commutative contract.

Under the table transactions

In insurance industry it happens sometimes that a client wants to switch from one insurer to another, the two insurers do an under the table transaction and the first one get some benefits and then shifts the policy to the other.

This practice can't be allowed in Takaful at any cost because it might be called a type of bribe. Some practitioners think that it is also a reason of not transferring to Takaful.

Negative propaganda

Few practitioners of the Takaful industry think that there is negative propaganda against the services of Takaful companies which results in disbelieve of the business community in Takaful. They prefer insurance over Takaful for this propaganda.

Less number of Re-Takaful operators

One of the challenges for the Takaful industry is their small capacity of covering big losses. This is because of the less number of Re-Takaful operators globally. Islamic banks can work together to solve this problem. They can establish Re-Takaful companies and this will lead to building more trust on the industry.

Establishing Re-Takaful companies from Islamic banks will not be a new sort of work as Islamic banks have established Takaful companies in the early era of the Islamic finance.

Islamic Insurance Company of Sudan was established by Fysal Islamic Bank of Sudan in 1979. This was the first ever Takaful company of the world and was established by an Islamic bank.

Islamic Arab Insurance Company was also established by an Islamic bank in the same year. It was established by Dubai Islamic Bank.

International Islamic Insurance Company of Bahrain is one of those companies which

have the major contribution of Islamic banks.

Conclusion:

It may be concluded by the above study that Islamic finance is growing rapidly and its basic components should increase in their correlation for the success of the industry as a whole specially the correlation of Islamic banks and Takaful should be more powerful. This might be if Islamic banks get Takaful coverage for their fixed assets and on the both sides of their business consumer and corporate. Takaful companies face many challenges which must be solved so the Islamic banks may feel relax in taking their services. The upper management of Islamic banks should be trained not only to fulfill the formality of SBP but to get the mindset which only wants to promote the Islamic finance industry as a whole.

References

Ahmed, Mohamed Helmy, Risk Management in Islamic Banks, ESLSCA Business Scholl, 2012

Grace, M.F, and Rebello, M.J., Financing and the demand for corporate insurance, The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance, 18, pp.147-72, 1993

Lewis, M.K., Liquidity. In Foundations of Economic Thought, Edited by J. Creedy. London: Basil Blackwell, 1990

Lorent, Benjamin, The Link between Insurance and Banking Sectors: An International Cross-Section Analysis of Life Insurance, Solvay Brussels School of Economics and Management, 2010

PAN, Gouchen, Jingyan GUO and Qiaoling JING, The Relationship between Insurance Industry and Banking Sector in China: Asymmetric Granger Causality Test, Romanian Journal of Economic Forecasting- XIX (2), 2016.

Qorchi, Mohammed El, Islamic Finance Gears Up, Finance & Development, December 2005, Vol 42.

Saleem, Shahid, Role of Islamic Banks in Economic Development, Graduate research submitted to Hailey College of Banking and Finance, University of Punjab, Lahore, 2008.

Trokic, Amela, An Analysis of Takaful: The Potential and Role in Financial Inclusion and Challenges Ahead, European Journal of Islamic Finance, 2017

Zou, H. and Adams, M.B., The corporate purchase of property insurance: Chinese

evidence, Journal of Financial Intermediation, 15, pp. 96-156, 2006

¹ Islamic Financial Services Board, Islamic Financial Services Industry Stability Report, May 2017, Kuala Lumpur

² SBP-Islamic Bulletin Report, June 2017, Karachi

³ <https://tribune.com.pk/436774/exploring-new-horizons-meezan-bank-eyes-entry-into-takaful-industry>, visited on 26/11/2017

ROLE OF ISLAMIC BANKING & TAKAFUL FOR GROWTH OF EACH OTHER

ORIGINALITY REPORT

5%

SIMILARITY INDEX

3%

INTERNET SOURCES

3%

PUBLICATIONS

1%

STUDENT PAPERS

PRIMARY SOURCES

1	www.islamicfinancenews.com Internet Source	2%
2	Syeda Fahmida Habib. "Fundamentals of Islamic Finance and Banking", Wiley, 2018 Publication	2%
3	ipe.ro Internet Source	1%
4	www.ojs.unito.it Internet Source	<1%
5	"Islamic Development Management", Springer Science and Business Media LLC, 2019 Publication	<1%
6	link.springer.com Internet Source	<1%

Exclude quotes Off

Exclude matches Off

Exclude bibliography On

ROLE OF ISLAMIC BANKING & TAKAFUL FOR GROWTH OF EACH OTHER

GRADEMARK REPORT

FINAL GRADE

/0

GENERAL COMMENTS

Instructor

PAGE 1

PAGE 2

PAGE 3

PAGE 4

PAGE 5

PAGE 6

PAGE 7

PAGE 8

Meezan Human Rights & Welfare Organization.

A-20, Sector U-1, Gulshan-e-Maymar, Karachi, Pakistan.75340

admin@narjss.com / info@narjss.com

NOOR UL ANWAR RESEARCH JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

Vol 02 Issue 01 2022

Article Evaluation Form

Title of Article:

Role of Islamic Banking & Takaful for Growth of Each Other

S.No	Analysis	تجزیہ	Agreed	Not Agreed
1	Abstract cover the scope of research paper	خلاصے میں مقالے کا مناسب احاطہ کیا گیا ہے۔	✓	
2	Paper is based on proper introduction and beginning	مقالہ مناسب ابتدائی اور تعارف پر مشتمل ہے۔	✓	
3	Method is relevant and based on research	مقالہ میں طریقہ کار تحقیقی اور مستند ہے۔	✓	
4	Presentation of information has expression & unity	معلومات کی فراہمی میں اظہار و ہم آہنگی ہے۔	✓	
5	Research paper covers the topic	مقالہ میں موضوع سے متعلق مواد موجود ہے۔	✓	
6	Paper is not contradiction to the basic Islamic believes	مقالہ مسلمہ بنیادی عقائد سے متصادم نہیں۔	✓	
7	Text of Quran and hadith is authentic	مقالہ میں آیات و احادیث کا متن درست ہے۔	✓	
8	Research paper is based on primary sources	مقالہ زیادہ تر بنیادی مصادر پر مشتمل ہے۔	✓	
9	Year & publications of references are correct	حوالہ جات میں مکتبہ تاریخ و غیرہ کا اندراج درست ہے۔	✓	
10	Impartial views are seen in the research paper	مقالہ نگار، مقالے کی تحریر میں غیر جانبدار ہے۔	✓	
11	Research paper is not just a copy paste / plagiarism	مقالہ علمی سرتقہ سے مبرا ہے۔	✓	
12	Research paper contributes in research works	مقالہ اہم تحقیقی کام ہے۔	✓	
13	Research paper is use full for the readers	مقالہ قارئین کے استفادہ کے لئے مفید ہے۔	✓	

اصلاح و ترمیم اگر کوئی ہو

- _____
- _____
- _____

<u>Overall Impression of Article</u>		
Rejected نا قابل اشاعت	Considerable after prescribed Amendments اصلاح و ترمیم کے بعد شائع کیا جائے	Selected قابل اشاعت
		✓

Name: Dr. Ubaid Ahmed Khan

Designation: Professor

Department: Department of Usooluddin

University: University of Karachi

Cell: 03218228263

Email: drubaidahmedkhan@gmail.com

PROF. DR. OBAID AHMED KHAN
Department of Usooluddin
University of Karachi.

(Stamp) Required as per HEC Rule

Meezan Human Rights & Welfare Organization.

A-20, Sector U-1, Gulshan-e-Maymar, Karachi, Pakistan.75340

admin@narjss.com / info@narjss.com

NOOR UL ANWAR RESEARCH JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

Vol 02 Issue 01 2022

Article Evaluation Form

Title of Article:

Role of Islamic Banking & Takaful for Growth of Each Other

S.No	Analysis	تجزیہ	Agreed	Not Agreed
1	Abstract cover the scope of research paper	خلاصے میں مقالے کا مناسب احاطہ کیا گیا ہے۔	Agreed	
2	Paper is based on proper introduction and beginning	مقالہ مناسب ابتدائی اور تعارف پر مشتمل ہے۔	Agreed	
3	Method is relevant and based on research	مقالہ میں طریقہ کار تحقیقی اور مستند ہے۔	Agreed	
4	Presentation of information has expression & unity	معلومات کی فراہمی میں اظہار و ہم آہنگی ہے۔	Agreed	
5	Research paper covers the topic	مقالہ میں موضوع سے متعلق مواد موجود ہے۔	Agreed	
6	Paper is not contradiction to the basic Islamic believes	مقالہ مسلمہ بنیادی عقائد سے متصادم نہیں۔	Agreed	
7	Text of Quran and hadith is authentic	مقالہ میں آیات و احادیث کا متن درست ہے۔	Agreed	
8	Research paper is based on primary sources	مقالہ زیادہ تر بنیادی مصادر پر مشتمل ہے۔	Agreed	
9	Year & publications of references are correct	حوالہ جات میں مکتبہ تاریخ و غیرہ کا اندراج درست ہے۔	Agreed	
10	Impartial views are seen in the research paper	مقالہ نگار، مقالے کی تحریر میں غیر جانبدار ہے۔	Agreed	
11	Research paper is not just a copy paste / plagiarism	مقالہ علمی سرتقہ سے مبرا ہے۔	Agreed	
12	Research paper contributes in research works	مقالہ اہم تحقیقی کام ہے۔	Agreed	
13	Research paper is use full for the readers	مقالہ قارئین کے استفادہ کے لئے مفید ہے۔	Agreed	

اصلاح و ترمیم اگر کوئی ہو

- _____
- _____
- _____

<u>Overall Impression of Article</u>		
Rejected نا قابل اشاعت	Considerable after prescribed Amendments اصلاح و ترمیم کے بعد شائع کیا جائے	Selected قابل اشاعت
		Agreed

Name: **Dr. Muhammad Rehan**

Designation: Assistant Professor

Department: Department of Basic Sciences

University: Muhammad Ali Jinnah University Karachi

Cell: 03092607362

Email: rehan.khan@jinnah.edu

Dr. Muhammad Rehan
Assistant Professor
Department of Basic Sciences
Muhammad Ali Jinnah University

(Stamp) Required as per HEC Rule

Meezan Human Rights & Welfare Organization.

A-20, Sector U-1, Gulshan-e-Maymar, Karachi, Pakistan.75340

admin@narjss.com / info@narjss.com

NOOR UL ANWAR RESEARCH JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

Vol 02 Issue 01 2022

Article Evaluation Form

Title of Article:

Role of Islamic Banking & Takaful for Growth of Each Other

S.No	Analysis	تجزیہ	Agreed	Not Agreed
1	Abstract cover the scope of research paper	خلاصے میں مقالے کا مناسب احاطہ کیا گیا ہے۔	Yes	
2	Paper is based on paper introduction and beginning	مقالہ مناسب ابتدا ہے اور تعارف پر مشتمل ہے۔	Yes	
3	Method is relevance and based on research	مقالہ میں طریقہ کار تحقیقی اور نسبتی ہے۔	Yes	
4	Presentation of information has expression & unit	معلومات کی فراہمی میں اظہار و ہم آہنگی ہے۔	Yes	
5	Research paper covers the topic	مقالہ میں موضوع سے متعلق مواد موجود ہے۔	Yes	
6	Paper is not contradiction to the basic Islamic believes	مقالہ مسلمہ بنیادی عقائد سے متصادم نہیں۔	Yes	
7	Text of Quran and hadith is authentic	مقالہ میں آیات و احادیث کا متن درست ہے۔	Yes	
8	Research paper is based on primary sources	مقالہ زیادہ تر بنیادی مصادر پر مشتمل ہے۔	Yes	
9	Year & publications of references are correct	حوالہ جات میں مکتبہ تاریخ و غیرہ کا اندراج درست ہے۔	Yes	
10	Impartial views are seen in the research paper	مقالہ نگار، مقالے کی تحریر میں غیر جانبدار ہے۔	Yes	
11	Research paper is not just a copy paste / plagiarism	مقالہ علمی سرقت سے مبرا ہے۔	Yes	
12	Research paper contributes in research works	مقالہ اہم تحقیقی کام ہے۔	Yes	
13	Research paper is use full for the readers	مقالہ قارئین کے استفادہ کے لئے مفید ہے۔	Yes	

اصلاح و ترمیم اگر کوئی ہو

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Overall Impression of Article

Rejected ناقابل اشاعت	Considerable after prescribed Amendments اصلاح و ترمیم کے بعد شائع کیا جائے	Selected قابل اشاعت
		Yes

Name: Dr. Tahira Firdous

Designation: Assistant Professor

Department: Faculty of Islamic Studies,

University: University of Balochistan, Saryab Road Quetta, Pakistan.

Cell: 03337046954

Email: drtahirairfan@gmail.com

DR. TAHIRA FIRDOUS
Assistant Professor
Department Islamic Studies
University of Baluchistan, Quetta

(Stamp) Required as per HEC Rule